

ISic2938

I.Sicily inscription 2938

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building; dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

Found in stores by Nenci

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG2007

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332182

1. [τοῖς] Δι [οσκούροις]
2. [οἱ τριτίρε] γες καὶ οἱ ἄνδ ρ [ες]
3. [συγκατασκ] ξυασθέντες.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644847

EDCS 70900012

PHI 332182

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 41.0826

De Vido, S. 1991. appendice: fonti letterarie, epigrafiche, numismatiche, etc.. *ASNP*. 21: 929-994. At 973

Nenci, G. 1991. Florilegio epigrafico segestano. *Annali della scuola normale superiore di Pisa*. 21: 920-929. At 921-922 no.1 tav.296

De Vido, S. 2003. Genealogie Segestane. *Quarte Giornate Internazionali di Studi sull'area elima, Erice, 1-4 dicembre 2000*. Pisa. pp. 367-402. At 399 no.9

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. *Inscriptiones Segestanae. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Segesta*. Pisa. At G13

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2938. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387761>